
Financial Support and Lecturers' Capacity Development in Public Universities in Rivers State

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Abstract

This study examined the relationship between financial support and lecturers' capacity development in public universities in Rivers State, Nigeria. One objective, one research question guided the study. One null hypothesis was tested at 0.05 significance level. The study adopted a correlational research design. The population comprised 4,503 lecturers serving in the three public universities in Rivers State. A sample size of 375 lecturers was selected using stratified and simple random sampling techniques were employed to draw respondents from each of the three university. Data were generated using two validated instruments. The instruments yielded reliability coefficients of 0.87 and 0.74 respectively. Research question was answered and the hypothesis was tested using Pearson's Product Moment Correlation. The findings revealed that financial support had a strong and significant relationship with lecturers' capacity development ($r = 0.645$, $r^2 = 0.416$, $p < 0.05$). The study concluded based on the findings that financial support has a high and significant positive relationship with lecturers' capacity development in public universities in Rivers State. This study therefore recommended that University governing councils and the Federal and State Ministries of Education should prioritise the consistent and adequate provision of financial support for lecturers. Such funding should cover research grants, conference sponsorship, and professional training programmes, as these are critical for sustaining high levels of capacity development.

Keywords: Financial support, lecturers' capacity development, public universities, Rivers State

Introduction

In Nigerian public universities, however, capacity development remains more of a necessity than an institutional norm. Iwu et al. (2022) observed that professional stagnation among lecturers often results from an absence of deliberate systems to support continuous learning and innovation. Yet, without targeted interventions to facilitate this growth, lecturers' performance may fall short of international expectations.

Financial support has significant impact on the capacity development of lecturers as it enables them undertake capital intensive but enrichment programmes and projects that can enhance their capacity. Financial support includes grants, conference sponsorships at local, regional and international levels, funding for scholarly work and professional development activities (Apple & Mills, 2022). Falola et al. (2020) remarked that adequate funding boosts motivation and reduces reliance on personal funds. Yet, in many Nigerian public universities, insufficient financial support, delays in fund release, unclear fund accessibility criteria, and limited incentives to motivate lecturers hinder lecturers' capacity development (Awojide, 2023). However, studies have shown that numerous challenges have limited the capacity of lecturers to deliver on the said expectations. Central to these challenges is the issue of inadequate institutional support, which ranges from insufficient funding, obsolete facilities, inadequate technology, and absence of professional development structures and all of which pose serious threats to the performance, productivity and well-being of lecturers. The researcher's personal observation further indicated that many public universities in Rivers State lack adequate classroom infrastructure and digital tools necessary for effective teaching and research, indicating that the capacity development challenge is somewhat rooted in systemic institutional neglect. The consequence of this protracted problem is a gradual erosion of teaching quality, a decline in research output, and a widening disconnect between university mandates and societal needs. These gaps diminish lecturers' potential to contribute meaningfully to intellectual advancement and stifle their continuous learning.

Forms of Institutional Support in Universities.

Institutional Support in universities comes in monetary and non-monetary forms. Monetary support involves research grants, support for attending conferences and workshops, fellowships, funding for sabbaticals, and funding for other professional development opportunities. Monetary support also involves providing money for procure the resources needed to support teaching, research, capacity development and innovation which and can attract and retain top talents.

Non-monetary support could be in the form of informational, emotional, social, practical help, encouragement, providing feedback, motivation, recognition for excellence. It could also involve promoting and facilitating enhancement activities, such as collaboration and networking activities aimed at providing opportunities for lecturers to connect with professionals in their field and engage with local communities to enhance knowledge sharing and skill improvement.

Also, while some scholars often categorize institutional support into structural, professional, emotional, and policy-based components, recognizing that a truly supportive institution addresses multiple aspects of the academic experience (Banda & Chigona, 2021), others have listed institutional support to include well-equipped libraries, access to academic databases, modern classrooms, research laboratories, and reliable internet services (Okonkwo & Nwosu, 2022).

Support could also come in the form of providing access to resources such as libraries, laboratories, technology and facilities, or in the form of providing work environment that promotes diversity, equity and inclusion through activities such as training programmes. These forms of non-monetary support can help universities foster a supportive and inclusive work environment that enhances the overall wellbeing of lecturers. For lecturers in public universities in Rivers State, access to these various forms of institutional support can become the difference between producing cutting-edge research and struggling to keep up with global academic standards.

Statement of the Problem

Lecturers in public universities in Rivers State are burdened with multifaceted expectations: they are to excel in teaching, drive innovative research, and engage in meaningful community service. These roles are not only foundational to institutional excellence but are also critical to national development. However, many of the lecturers often express concern over lack of meaningful and sustained efforts towards addressing the largely persistent structural and institutional challenges that have been constraining their capacity to deliver on the said expectations. Central to these challenges ranging from insufficient funding, obsolete facilities, and absence of professional development structures, all of which pose serious threats to the productivity and well-being of academic staff. The consequence of these protracted bedeviling issues is a gradual and consistent erosion of teaching quality, a decline in research output, and a widening disconnect between university mandates and societal needs. It is against this backdrop that the researcher examined the relationship between institutional support and lecturers' capacity development in public universities in Rivers State, Nigeria.

Aim and Objective of the Study

The aim examined the relationship between institutional support and lecturers' capacity development in public universities in Rivers State, Nigeria. Specifically, the objective sought to:

1. Determine the relationship between financial support and lecturers' capacity development in public universities in Rivers State.

Research Question

The research question guided this study:

1. What is the relationship between financial support and lecturers' capacity development in public universities in Rivers State?

Hypothesis

The hypothesis was formulated and tested in the study at 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant relationship between financial support and lecturers' capacity development in public universities in Rivers State universities in Rivers State.

Literature Review

University Lecturers

Lecturers are the teaching staff of tertiary institutions who are gainfully employed with the sole aim of knowledge production and dissemination. In the university, lecturers hold an academic rank with titles such as professor, associate professor, assistant professor and lecturer. They are the indispensable assets of higher educational institutions to which public university is one (Teferra, 2021). They are at the center of the education process and are responsible for attaining the educational goals of institutions and society at large, and are directed towards shaping the destinies of individuals and development of nations. The

success of any educational institution, its increased productivity, the quality of students turned out are all greatly dependent on the lecturer's effectiveness. (Omodan & Ige, 2021)

The primary assignment of lecturers is teaching, research, and public service. They are extensively involved in teaching, and lecturing remains the dominant teaching method in universities. Other teaching methods include seminars, tutorials, and workshops. Lecturers are engaged in conducting research, publishing scholarly articles, and presenting research findings. They supervise student research; guide students in their research projects, theses, and dissertations, develop and publish academic materials such as textbooks, academic papers, and other scholarly materials. They develop and administer assessments, exams, and evaluations to measure student learning, provide constructive feedback and grades to students on their performance.

The role of the lecturer also involves service and community engagement such as departmental and university Service; They participate in departmental and university committees, task forces, and work in groups, engage in outreach and partnership activities with local communities, industries, and organizations. They also participate in professional development activities, conferences, and workshops to stay current in their field.

In addition, lecturers take up roles like student support and advising; providing guidance and advice to students on academic matters, such as course selection and degree requirements, mentoring students in their academic and professional development, supporting students with disabilities and special needs. Lecturers also perform administrative and leadership roles such as program coordination and management of academic programs, including curriculum development and program evaluation. They serve as department chairs, directors, or other leadership roles, participates in university-wide committees, such as those focused on curriculum, research, or student affairs. Other responsibilities performed by the lecturer include engaging in ongoing professional development to stay current with the latest developments in their field contributing to accreditation and quality assurance processes to ensure the quality of academic programs.

These functions highlight the diverse and demanding role of a university lecturer indicating that the roles of the university lecturers are quite complex, time consuming and its context is constantly changing. Meeting up with these challenges require a high level of competence on the part of the lecturer who is at the center of the teaching process. Effective lecture delivery depends to a large extent, on the quality of the strategies adopted by the lecturer. For this reason, the lecturers' capacity needs to be continuously developed for them to be adequately equipped for the job (Akuegwu, Nwi-Ue, & Eno 2013).

Lecturers Need for Capacity Development

Lecturers cannot be taken for granted or viewed simply as skilled technicians who dutifully realize a given set of teaching in accordance with the directives of management. Lecturers are supposed to be active participants in the creation of classroom realities (Mafungu & Abel, 2022). Since lecturers play a vital role in shaping students' academic experiences, advancing knowledge in their field, and contributing to the universities mission. They need to have an understanding of , and be interested in how students learn, they need to develop key skills and qualities such as written and verbal communication skills, teaching skills, research and analytical skills, leadership, collaboration, time management, organization skills and strong relationship-building skills to build networks. They also need to be able to engage in continuous learning in order to build their expertise. Acquiring these skills help to develop the capacity of lecturers. Ajirolore-Chukwuemeka, (2023) argued that

“education is too complicated to be done without intentionally learning how to do it” and that “lecturers need help beyond themselves”

Capacity development is a complex, multifaceted process that lies at the heart of academic excellence and institutional progress. For university lecturers, it is both a personal and collective endeavor, shaped by individual ambition, institutional support, and systemic policy frameworks. In the Nigerian context, and particularly in public universities, capacity development is not just a pathway to professional success but a critical lever for national development.

By investing in robust capacity development initiatives, universities can empower lecturers to reach their full potential, transforming their institutions into hubs of innovation, knowledge production, and societal impact. Ultimately, capacity development is about more than just building skills; it is about nurturing a culture of continuous learning, intellectual curiosity, and scholarly excellence that propels universities and the societies they serve toward a brighter future.

Methodology

The design adopted for this study was the correlational survey design. The population of this study comprised all the 4,503 academic staff serving in the three public universities in Rivers State. These included the University of Port Harcourt (UNIPORT), Rivers State University (RSU), and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education (IAUE). The sample size for this study was 375 lecturers. This was determined using stratified random sampling technique was employed to ensure fair representation of lecturers across the three institutions. To ensure that the instruments used in this study possessed both face validity and content validity, the draft versions of the Financial Support Assessment Questionnaire (FSAQ) and the Lecturers’ Capacity Development Questionnaire (LCDQ) were subjected to expert review. The reliability of the instruments was done using Cronbach Alpha method. A reliability coefficients obtained for FSAQ was 0.87 while the reliability coefficients for LCDQ was 0.78 indicating that the instruments were substantially reliable and suitable for use in the main study. The research question was answered using Pearson product moment correlation and hypothesis tested at 0.05 alpha level using z-test.

Results

Research Question One: What is the relationship between financial support and lecturers’ capacity development in public universities in Rivers State?

Table 1: Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) on the relationship between financial support and lecturers’ capacity development in public universities in Rivers State.

Variables	N	Df	R	Degree of Relationship
Financial Support	371	369	0.645	Very High
Capacity Development				

Decision rule: .01 - .24 = low relationship, .25 - .45 = moderate relationship, .50 - .74 high relationship, and 0.75 – 1.0 = Very High relationship.

Table 1 presents the summary of simple linear correlation analysis which examined the extent of relationship between financial support and lecturers' capacity development in public universities. The result shows a Pearson R value of .645, which indicates a high positive correlation between financial support and lecturers' capacity development. This result indicates that adequate financial support plays a meaningful role in explaining the professional growth and development of lecturers.

Test of Null Hypothesis

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between financial support and lecturers' capacity development in public universities in Rivers State universities in Rivers State.

Table 2: Analysis of z-test of the relationship between financial support and lecturers' capacity development in public universities in Rivers State universities in Rivers State

Variables	N	Df	R	z-cal	z-crit.	Decision
Financial Support Capacity development	371	369	0.645	14.71	±1.96	Reject H ₀₁ , significant

Table 2 presents the result of the test of significance of the relationship between financial support and lecturers' capacity development in public universities in Rivers State. The analysis yielded a correlation coefficient of $r=0.645$ with a corresponding z-test statistic of 14.71. Since the obtained z-value of 14.71 is by far higher than the z-critical value of ± 1.96 at the 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis is rejected. This confirms that there is a high positive and statistically significant relationship between financial support and lecturers' capacity development in public universities in Rivers State.

Findings

Financial Support and Lecturers' Capacity Development

The analysis of data obtained for this study revealed a high and significant relationship between financial support and lecturers' capacity development in public universities in Rivers State ($r = .645$; $p < .05$). This substantial finding underscores the critical role that direct financial input plays in enhancing academic staff capacity, both in terms of research productivity and professional development. Adequate financial support ensures that lecturers can attend conferences, undertake research, subscribe to academic journals, and enrol in further training programmes, all of which are essential for sustained growth in a knowledge-intensive profession. This result aligns with the findings of Iyala and Tamunosiki (2020), who observed that funding was significantly and positively associated with staff development in Rivers State universities. In their study, a strong relationship ($r = 0.75$) was reported between financial input and the provision of staff training opportunities. This suggests that, even within similar local institutional contexts, funding is consistently a lever for enhancing human capital development.

The relevance of financial support in promoting lecturer development is further emphasised in the study conducted by Okorie and Nnamdi (2020), which examined the role of mentorship in grant acquisition. Although focused on mentorship, their findings clearly indicated that lecturers who received guidance in grant writing were significantly more successful in securing research funding. This speaks to the interdependence between financial resources and the institutional structures that enable access to them. Financial support in isolation may

have limited impact unless paired with structured mechanisms to guide access and utilisation. Nonetheless, the availability of funds remains the necessary first condition. In the absence of sufficient funds allocated for research and development, lecturers' professional growth is stunted, irrespective of institutional goodwill. Ekpo et al. (2023) provided evidence that the provision of research grants and in-service training, both of which are forms of financial support significantly improved lecturers' professional competencies in Nigerian universities. Their study found that institutions with strong policy frameworks on funding mechanisms were more likely to report higher staff development outcomes. This implies that financial support is not only a material input but also a function of institutional policy commitment. Policies that prioritise allocation of funds for training and research create the structural environment for capacity development to thrive. A contrasting picture emerges in institutions where such policies are weak or inconsistently implemented, resulting in fragmented or short-lived capacity-building initiatives.

In addition to national-level studies, findings from Ogun and Adebisi (2023) further illustrate the value of financial investment through their work on virtual libraries, which are typically funded through institutional or external grants. Their study revealed a 40% increase in lecturer publications in universities with access to well-funded digital libraries, demonstrating that targeted financial support towards academic resources has a measurable impact on capacity development. This aligns directly with the current study's finding, as access to digital materials enhances lecturers' ability to engage with contemporary research, thereby enriching their teaching and scholarly output. Financial support in this sense becomes both a direct and indirect enabler that support not only training and travel but also resourcing the academic environment. When this support is consistent and equitable, it creates a platform for sustainable capacity development. Thus, the conclusion that financial support significantly influences lecturers' capacity development is not merely supported by local data, but also reflects a coherent pattern across the broader Nigerian university system. Institutional investment, when directed with strategic foresight, serves not only to equip lecturers but to elevate the intellectual profile of universities themselves.

5.0 Conclusion

The study concluded based on the findings that financial support has a high and significant positive relationship with lecturers' capacity development, while informational support showed a moderate and significant positive relationship.

6.0 Recommendation

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendation was made by the researcher.

1. University governing councils and the Federal and State Ministries of Education should prioritise the consistent and adequate provision of financial support for lecturers. Such funding should cover research grants, conference sponsorship, and professional training programmes, as these are critical for sustaining high levels of capacity development.

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